

Students and Teachers' Perception on the Use of Technology in English Learning at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga

Nazwa Natasya Keysha Maga

¹²Program Studi Pendidikan Bahasa Inggris, Fakultas Sastra dan Budaya, Universitas Negeri Gorontalo

Email: nazwamaga23@gmail.com

Abstrak

Penelitian ini mengkaji persepsi siswa dan guru terhadap penggunaan teknologi dalam pembelajaran bahasa Inggris di SMA Negeri 1 Telaga. Integrasi alat digital seperti YouTube, Duolingo, Grammarly, Lyrics Training, e-book, proyektor LCD, Canva, dan Quizizz telah mengubah pengajaran bahasa Inggris menjadi pengalaman yang lebih interaktif dan menarik. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk memahami bagaimana kedua kelompok memandang manfaat, tantangan, dan efektivitas teknologi dalam meningkatkan keterampilan bahasa dan motivasi belajar. Dengan menggunakan pendekatan campuran (mixed-method), data dikumpulkan melalui kuesioner (melibatkan 37 siswa dan 5 guru) dan wawancara (dengan 3 siswa dan 2 guru). Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa sebagian besar guru memiliki kemampuan teknologi yang memadai dan secara aktif menggunakan berbagai alat digital untuk mendukung pembelajaran. Namun, beberapa guru, khususnya yang berusia lebih tua, menghadapi tantangan karena keterbatasan pengalaman dan pelatihan. Siswa pada umumnya menunjukkan preferensi yang kuat terhadap pembelajaran berbasis teknologi, dengan melaporkan peningkatan motivasi, keterlibatan, dan peluang untuk belajar secara mandiri. Meski demikian, masih terdapat beberapa kendala, seperti keterbatasan infrastruktur sekolah, akses internet yang tidak stabil, dan gangguan dari media sosial. Terlepas dari hambatan tersebut, integrasi teknologi dipandang bermanfaat oleh guru dan siswa, menunjukkan arah positif menuju pendidikan bahasa Inggris yang lebih dinamis dan efektif. Untuk memaksimalkan dampaknya, pelatihan profesional yang berkelanjutan bagi guru dan peningkatan infrastruktur sangatlah penting.

Kata kunci: *integrasi teknologi, pembelajaran bahasa Inggris, persepsi siswa, persepsi guru, SMA Negeri 1 Telaga, motivasi, alat digital.*

Abstract

This study investigates students' and teachers' perceptions of the use of technology in English learning at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga. The integration of digital tools such as YouTube, Duolingo, Grammarly, Lyrics Training, e-books, LCD projectors, Canva, and Quizizz has transformed English language instruction into a more interactive and engaging experience. The research aims to understand how both groups perceive the benefits, challenges, and effectiveness of technology in enhancing language skills and motivation. Employing a mixed-method approach, data were collected through questionnaires (involving 37 students and 5 teachers) and interviews (with 3 students and 2 teachers). The findings reveal that most teachers possess adequate technological proficiency and actively use various digital tools to support their teaching, although a few, particularly older teachers, face challenges due to limited experience and training. Students generally show a strong preference for technology-based learning, reporting increased motivation, engagement, and opportunities for independent learning. Nevertheless, several issues persist, including limited school infrastructure, inadequate access to stable internet, and distractions from social media. Despite these obstacles, the integration of technology is perceived as beneficial by both teachers and students, indicating a positive trajectory towards more dynamic and effective English language education. To maximize its impact, ongoing professional development for teachers and infrastructural improvements are essential.

Keywords: *technology integration, English learning, students' perception, teachers' perception, SMA Negeri 1 Telaga, motivation, digital tool*

Article Info

Received date: 15 May 2025

Revised date: 20 May 2025

Accepted date: 27 May 2025

INTRODUCTION

English is one of the essential subjects at the senior high school level, especially in an era of globalization that increasingly emphasizes the importance of cross-cultural skills and international communication. Proficiency in English has become a valuable asset for the younger generation, as it

enables them to access information from all over the world, communicate with people from different nations, and broaden their career opportunities in various fields. Moreover, rapid technological advancements have expanded the need for English comprehension, particularly in using technological tools such as software, applications, and scientific literature, which are predominantly presented in English.

Integrating technology into English learning at the senior high school level is crucial to support the development of students' language skills and prepare them to face increasingly complex global challenges. English proficiency serves not only as a communication tool but also as a gateway to accessing a wide range of information and opportunities in the international arena. One of the main reasons technology is important in English learning is its ability to provide access to a broader and more diverse range of learning resources. Technology enables students to explore learning materials beyond conventional textbooks, including articles, videos, podcasts, and e-books. Through online platforms like YouTube, students can view learning materials in a variety of native accents, which not only enriches their understanding in real-life contexts but also enhances their listening and speaking skills.

In addition, the integration of technology allows for a more interactive and engaging learning process. The use of interactive tools such as online quizzes (Kahoot, Quizizz), interactive videos, and game-based applications encourages students to actively participate in learning. Through gamification and challenge elements, students are more motivated and enthusiastic to master English. Technology also supports more personalized and adaptive learning, allowing students to learn at their own pace and according to their individual learning styles. The use of multimedia makes learning more dynamic and interesting by providing not only theoretical content but also practical experiences in using the language through listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills.

For instance, design platforms such as Canva allow teachers to create more visual and engaging teaching materials. Using Canva, teachers can design infographics, posters, and presentations that are more creative and easier for students to understand. This not only enriches classroom content but also provides variety in teaching methods, making the learning experience more enjoyable and increasing students' enthusiasm.

However, English language learning at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga still faces significant challenges, one of which is the low level of student engagement and motivation in the learning process. This issue is not only related to students' lack of interest in learning English but also to the limited variety of innovative teaching aids that meet students' needs. As a result, many students feel bored, unenthusiastic, or even disengaged during the learning process. Students often perceive English as a difficult and complicated subject, which lowers their motivation to explore the material further. The lack of technology integration in learning also contributes to the decline in student engagement. In fact, technology can enrich the learning experience through interactive tools such as learning videos, educational game applications, and other digital resources. If technology is not fully utilized, students will receive lessons through the same conventional methods, which eventually reduces their enthusiasm to participate actively in class.

At SMA Negeri 1 Telaga, both students and teachers have begun to use various technologies in classroom learning to improve the quality and effectiveness of the teaching and learning process. Students use YouTube to watch engaging and interactive educational videos, while Duolingo is used as a platform to practice and enhance their English skills. The Lyrics Training application helps students understand English song lyrics in a fun way, while Grammarly is used to improve their writing skills through automatic grammar correction. Digital reading sources such as e-books are also used as additional references to broaden students' knowledge. On the other hand, teachers also optimize the use of technology to deliver material in a more engaging and comprehensible manner. LCD projectors are used to visually present various learning media, while Canva is used to design more creative and appealing instructional content. In the assessment process, teachers use Quizizz as an interactive platform, making evaluations more enjoyable and motivating students to participate more actively in learning. With the integration of various technologies, the learning process at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga has become more dynamic, innovative, and aligned with modern developments.

Based on the issues described above, English teachers at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga have started implementing technology-integrated learning as an effort to improve student engagement and motivation. A study by Ferdinand (2023) revealed that the use of technology in learning is directly

related to high student motivation. The study showed that students exhibited very high motivation to learn English when educational technology was used effectively. This demonstrates that the use of technology not only enriches the learning process but also plays a vital role in increasing students' interest and involvement.

Furthermore, research by Syaadia (2020) supports this finding, stating that the use of technology can help students improve their English skills. Technology provides various resources and tools that support language learning, such as learning applications, interactive videos, and online platforms, which allow students to practice in a more engaging and enjoyable manner.

In the context of teaching at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga, teachers play a crucial role in integrating technology into the learning process. Their role is essential, as they must be able to utilize technology in ways that are relevant and meet students' needs. The use of technology is not merely a tool, but a means of transforming how students interact with the material, offering a more engaging learning experience, and preparing them to face future global challenges.

METHOD

This study employed a mixed methods approach, specifically the sequential explanatory design, which combines quantitative and qualitative methods. This design was chosen to provide a comprehensive and in-depth understanding of students' and teachers' perceptions regarding the use of technology in English learning at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga. As Creswell and Plano Clark (2007) suggest, the sequential explanatory design begins with the collection and analysis of quantitative data, followed by qualitative data collection to explain or expand upon the quantitative results.

The rationale for using this design is its ability to explore general trends through numerical data while also capturing detailed insights through participants' personal experiences and explanations. Quantitative data provides measurable results, while qualitative data offers contextual depth, allowing the study to present a holistic view of the phenomena under investigation.

Research Site

This study was conducted at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga. The location was selected due to the school's active integration of technology in English language teaching and learning. The research specifically focused on the perceptions of both students and teachers regarding the use of educational technology in English instruction.

Population and Sample

Population

According to Sugiyono (2019), population refers to the generalization region consisting of objects or subjects that have specific characteristics determined by the researcher. The population in this study includes all students and English teachers at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga who have experience with technology-based English learning.

Sample

The sample consisted of 37 students and 5 English teachers selected through purposive sampling. This technique ensured that only those with relevant experience in using technology for English learning were included. Students were drawn from grade X and XI to obtain a broader range of perspectives, while 3 students and 2 teachers were selected for interviews based on their active involvement with educational technology.

Purposive sampling, as defined by Sugiyono (2015), ensures that participants contribute meaningful data based on their knowledge and experience. This approach is expected to yield deeper insights into how technology supports or hinders English learning at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga.

Data Collection Techniques

Quantitative Data

Quantitative data were collected using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: the first gathered demographic information (e.g., name, age, gender), and the second included Likert-scale items to measure students' and teachers' perceptions of technology use in English learning. The Likert scale ranged from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree" for both positive and negative statements.

Qualitative Data

Qualitative data were collected through semi-structured interviews. According to Magaldi and Berler (2020), semi-structured interviews offer flexibility in exploring participants' experiences while still following a guide. The interviews included six main questions and were followed by spontaneous probing questions depending on the participant's responses. All interviews were recorded with consent and transcribed for further analysis.

Data Analysis Techniques

Quantitative Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically percentage calculations, based on the following formula:

Qualitative Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was used to analyze qualitative data. According to Alhojailan & Ibrahim (2012), thematic analysis involves identifying patterns or themes within qualitative data. The process followed Creswell's (1998) model as cited in Putra (2024):

1. Transcription: Interview recordings were transcribed.
2. Data Review: The researcher read the transcripts thoroughly to gain an overall understanding.
3. Data Categorization: Responses were grouped into themes based on the research focus.
4. Interpretation: Each theme was analyzed in depth to draw meaningful conclusions about participants' perceptions and experiences.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Students and Teachers' Perception on the Use of Technology in English Learning at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga

Teacher Perception on Basic Understanding of Technology in English Learning

Most teachers demonstrate a good foundational awareness of the technologies used in English learning, such as apps, digital platforms, and tools for lesson preparation and delivery. Around 80% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with statements related to their knowledge of these technologies, indicating a relatively high level of technological literacy among the teachers. However, about 20% disagreed, often citing age-related challenges or limited prior experience with digital tools. This variation suggests the presence of digital literacy gaps within the teaching staff, highlighting the need for targeted capacity-building to support those less familiar with educational technologies.

Teachers' Use of Technology in the Learning Process

Teachers commonly use technology for designing and presenting learning materials, with 80% regularly utilizing tools like Canva, PowerPoint, and LCD projectors. This shows a positive trend in adopting technology to enhance lesson engagement. However, technology use to support language skills development varies: 80% of teachers employ digital resources to improve listening skills, but fewer apply such tools for speaking (60%), reading (60%), and especially writing (40%). Challenges such as limited access, lack of training, and concerns about academic integrity with AI tools contribute to these discrepancies. Additionally, while 80% use technology to create more engaging evaluations, 20% remain hesitant, often due to comfort with traditional methods or technical barriers.

Teachers' Perception of Technology's Impact on Teaching and Learning

A majority of teachers (80%) perceive technology as beneficial in facilitating classroom teaching and enhancing student enthusiasm for learning English. They believe technology enriches instructional methods and supports student engagement through interactive media and applications. Similarly, 80% agree that technology positively impacts students' English skills development by providing diverse resources and encouraging independent practice. Nonetheless, 20% of teachers remain skeptical or face obstacles such as infrastructure limitations and insufficient training, which affect technology's effective integration. The absence of widespread "strongly agree" responses suggests that while technology is valued, it has yet to be fully embraced as indispensable in teaching practice.

Students' Perception of Basic Understanding of Technology in English Learning

The majority of students demonstrate good awareness and knowledge of technologies that can support English learning, such as applications, digital platforms, and interactive media. About 56.8% of students agreed and 43.2% strongly agreed that they know these technologies. This indicates that students already have a basic understanding of the benefits of technology in the learning process, and they feel confident that technology can help improve their English skills. While most students prefer learning methods that use technology, a small portion still does not fully support this approach.

Students' Perception of the Use of Technology in the Learning Process

Students perceive that technology greatly assists in developing various English skills. Most respondents stated that technology helps effectively improve listening and pronunciation skills, with over 90% agreeing. Additionally, technology provides automatic feedback on writing errors and offers engaging texts to enhance reading skills. However, some students expressed concerns about the accuracy of automatic feedback, indicating a need for further evaluation of the quality of learning applications.

Students' Perception of the Effectiveness of Technology Use in Learning

Students feel that the use of technology makes classroom learning more interesting and enjoyable. All respondents agreed that technology increases their motivation to learn and makes it easier to complete assignments. Furthermore, 100% of students reported improvements in their English skills when using technology. These findings show that technology is well accepted and has a significant positive impact on both the learning process and student outcomes.

Teacher Interview Result

The interview findings reveal that teachers at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga hold nuanced perceptions regarding the integration of technology in English language learning. They recognize the diverse benefits of technology while also highlighting significant challenges that affect its optimal use.

Firstly, teachers actively incorporate various technological tools such as LCD projectors, YouTube, Canva, and social media platforms to enrich teaching materials and make lessons more engaging. One teacher noted the use of social media for speaking tasks, which reflects an innovative approach to leveraging digital platforms for language practice. However, the practical challenges of technology setup sometimes limit its usage, as another teacher prefers direct instruction to avoid wasting class time on technical issues. This suggests that while technology has potential, its implementation is still constrained by logistical factors.

Secondly, both teachers agree that technology positively influences student motivation and engagement. Multimedia elements like videos and quizzes captivate students' interest and create a more dynamic learning environment. Yet, concerns about the time efficiency of technological tools highlight a tension between engagement and practical classroom management.

Thirdly, technology evidently supports the development of receptive skills such as listening and reading by providing access to authentic and varied materials. However, the assessment of productive skills, particularly writing and speaking, remains problematic due to students' use of AI tools. This issue raises questions about the authenticity of students' work and challenges teachers' ability to accurately evaluate language proficiency.

Moreover, teachers acknowledge that while technology enhances interactivity, it can also distract students from core content if not managed properly. This underlines the necessity of balanced integration strategies to ensure technology serves as a facilitator rather than a distraction.

Finally, the evaluation of technology's effectiveness relies heavily on observable student participation and understanding during discussions and presentations. However, the prevalence of AI use complicates the assessment of writing and speaking tasks, undermining teachers' confidence in measuring true learning outcomes.

In summary, the interviews illustrate a complex picture where technology significantly benefits motivation and skill development but simultaneously introduces challenges in authenticity assessment and classroom efficiency. To fully harness the advantages of technology, educators at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga must address these barriers by developing clearer guidelines, improving technical support, and adapting assessment methods to the realities of AI-assisted learning. This balanced approach will enable technology to fulfill its transformative potential in English education.

Students Interview Result

The interviews with students at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga revealed diverse perceptions regarding the use of technology in English learning. Students recognized various benefits of technology that support the learning process, while also identifying several challenges that need to be addressed to maximize the effectiveness of technology use.

First, students accessed a variety of learning sources utilizing technology, such as Google Translate, YouTube, Spotify, Duolingo, ChatGPT, and Grammarly. These platforms help them with translation, pronunciation training, vocabulary building, and checking grammar and writing. One student mentioned, "I often use Google Translate when I want to understand the text or to help with writing assignments." This shows that technology provides wide and easily accessible learning resources for independent study.

Second, students use technology for independent and flexible learning both during and outside school hours. They feel able to manage their learning time according to their personal needs, which increases comfort and learning effectiveness. One student said, "I study almost every day through videos, listening to podcasts, or playing Duolingo, not only when there are assignments." This indicates how technology facilitates more personalized and continuous learning.

Third, the role of technology in the classroom, especially through the use of LCD projectors and interactive applications like Quizizz, provides a more visual and interactive learning experience. Students feel that the material becomes clearer and learning is more enjoyable. "When teachers use the LCD projector to show videos, lessons become clearer and not boring," said a student. Furthermore, the interactivity provided by Quizizz livens up the classroom atmosphere and increases student participation.

Fourth, technology also significantly supports the improvement of listening and speaking skills through authentic content such as English videos, podcasts, and movies. Students become accustomed to various intonations and accents, making speaking practice more natural. One student stated, "I often imitate the intonation and speaking style from videos," showing how technology enables realistic and effective language practice.

Fifth, technology supports the development of reading and writing skills, for example, through subtitles in videos and applications like Grammarly that help correct grammar. However, some students still feel that the greatest impact of technology is on listening and speaking skills.

Nevertheless, students also identified several challenges, mainly related to inadequate technology facilities at school, such as lack of Wi-Fi and technical problems with LCD projectors. These obstacles hinder their access to online and interactive learning resources, thus limiting the effectiveness of technology-based learning. One student shared, "There is no Wi-Fi at school, so it's difficult to open YouTube or join quizzes like Quizizz."

Additionally, students expressed the need for differentiated materials suited to individual proficiency levels, especially for listening exercises that sometimes are too difficult for some students. This highlights that technology integration needs to be more adaptive to meet individual learning needs.

Managing technology use is also a concern, particularly distractions from social media when using phones in class. Therefore, students want clearer rules so that technology is used effectively for learning rather than entertainment.

Finally, students hope for more innovative technology integration and training so they can make the most of learning applications. Ideas like speaking challenges via video and regular interactive quizzes are desired to make English learning more engaging and effective.

Overall, students' perceptions indicate that technology plays an important role in increasing motivation, access to learning resources, and English language skills, especially in listening and speaking. However, successful technology integration is still hindered by facility limitations, the need for material differentiation, and managing technology use. Therefore, improving infrastructure, adapting materials, and implementing technology use policies in the classroom are crucial aspects to optimize the benefits of technology in English learning at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga.

DISCUSSION

Teachers' Perceptions on the Use of Technology

Most teachers at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga demonstrate a good level of technological proficiency, effectively using devices like laptops, LCD projectors, and applications such as PowerPoint and Canva to enhance English learning. Their willingness to adapt to technological advancements reflects the growing importance of technology in modern education. However, some teachers—mainly older ones—still face challenges due to limited experience and lack of training, relying more on traditional teaching methods and requiring further support.

Teachers acknowledge that technology plays a significant role in improving students' English skills, especially listening, supported by applications like BBC Learning English and TEDEd. While 60% agree technology enhances speaking skills, some prefer face-to-face interaction for communication development. Technology also helps with reading fluency through digital texts and e-books, but selecting appropriate tools remains challenging. In writing, teachers are cautious about over-reliance on AI, fearing it may hinder critical thinking and authenticity.

Technology aids teachers in student assessment by enabling dynamic and personalized evaluation, improving the efficiency of feedback and intervention. It also motivates and engages students by creating interactive learning environments with videos, music, and quizzes. Nonetheless, improper management can cause distractions, and preparation time for technology setup sometimes reduces actual teaching time.

Overall, teachers show positive attitudes toward technology use but emphasize the need for continuous professional development and infrastructure improvements to fully realize technology's benefits in English education.

Students' Perceptions on the Use of Technology

Students overwhelmingly prefer technology-enhanced learning over traditional methods, with 70.3% expressing greater motivation and engagement when digital tools are used. Technology makes learning more enjoyable and interactive, with educational videos and apps helping them understand material better and learn independently beyond classroom hours.

Despite these benefits, students face obstacles such as inadequate school facilities—unstable Wi-Fi and faulty devices—that limit their ability to use technology fully. Distractions from social media apps like Instagram and TikTok also pose challenges to maintaining focus during lessons, highlighting the need for clear rules on technology use in classrooms.

Students' positive views affirm that technology increases interest and supports flexible, personalized learning. However, infrastructure improvements and stronger institutional support are essential to overcome current barriers and optimize the effectiveness of technology-based English learning.

Students' and teachers' perception on use of technology in English learning.

Students' and teachers' perceptions of technology use in English language learning at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga reveals a significant gap in several key aspects. In terms of basic understanding

(absorption), students show high enthusiasm and readiness. They are already familiar with using various applications and digital platforms such as YouTube, Duolingo, Grammarly, and Google Classroom. This indicates that students, as digital natives, are quicker to adapt and more open to the use of technology in the learning process. Meanwhile, although most teachers have a good understanding of technology and are capable of using tools such as laptops, LCD projectors, PowerPoint, and Canva, a small number—especially older teachers—still struggle with mastering technology due to limited training and experience. This aligns with Hapsari's (2023) findings, which state that teachers in Indonesia show high readiness to use technology, but still face challenges in integrating technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge. This adaptation challenge is significant, especially when students themselves are already more prepared for technology-based learning.

In terms of practical application in the learning process (understanding), students experience direct benefits from technology in improving their language skills—listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Technology is perceived as making learning more engaging, interactive, and flexible, while also providing access to diverse learning resources. On the other hand, teachers tend to use technology in a limited way, mostly for creating presentation materials or visual media. Only a small portion of teachers deeply integrate technology to develop students' language skills. Some still rely on conventional methods, especially for speaking skills, believing that direct interaction is more effective in training students' social and emotional communication. This shows that even though the technology is available, not all teachers have strong pedagogical capacity to fully leverage it in skills-based learning.

In terms of evaluation, students feel that technology helps them learn independently and enables more flexible learning. They also report feeling more motivated and engaged in class when digital media is used. However, they also face challenges such as limited school facilities, unstable Wi-Fi, and distractions from social media that can reduce concentration. On the teachers' side, many acknowledge that technology facilitates the evaluation process, for example, through platforms that provide automatic and real-time feedback. However, they are also concerned about academic integrity, particularly in writing and speaking tasks, due to the increasing reliance on technology and AI that may compromise the authenticity of students' learning outcomes. This concern is supported by Cardon (2023), who notes that one of the main perceived challenges among educators is the fear that AI-assisted tools reduce the authenticity of students' written work. Teachers worry that reliance on generative AI could diminish students' critical thinking and originality, thereby affecting the quality and academic honesty of their assignments. This issue calls for clear guidelines on the use of AI in learning, as well as the cultivation of academic integrity values among students.

Overall, although both teachers and students have positive views of technology use, students appear to be more prepared and enthusiastic in applying it to English language learning. This highlights the need to enhance teachers' capacity through ongoing technology training, particularly in integrating pedagogy, content, and technology holistically. In addition, adequate infrastructure and supportive policies are essential to ensure ethical and effective technology use. By doing so, the gap in perceptions and practices can be bridged, allowing for the optimal use of technology in learning, supporting the development of language skills, and preserving academic integrity.

CONCLUSION

The integration of technology into English language learning at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga has demonstrated significant potential to improve both the teaching and learning experiences. The majority of teachers at the school have shown a commendable level of proficiency in utilizing various technological tools, such as laptops, LCD projectors, and applications like PowerPoint and Canva. These tools enable teachers to create more engaging and interactive lessons, which enhance students' understanding and participation. The ability of teachers to effectively use these technologies highlights their willingness to adapt to the rapid advancements in technology, which have become an essential aspect of modern education. This adoption of technological tools is not only helping in the delivery of lessons but also in fostering an environment that encourages dynamic learning experiences.

Despite these positive developments, challenges persist, particularly for a small number of teachers who find it difficult to use technology effectively. Factors such as age, limited experience with digital tools, and a lack of adequate training hinder their ability to integrate technology into their

teaching practices. These teachers often rely on traditional teaching methods, which can limit the effectiveness of their lessons in comparison to their more tech-savvy counterparts. For these educators, additional support, in the form of professional development and training on technology usage, is necessary. By addressing these challenges, the school can ensure that all teachers are equipped with the necessary skills to leverage technology in their teaching, thereby ensuring a more uniform and effective educational experience for all students.

On the students' side, there is a clear preference for technology-based learning methods. The majority of students find technology-enhanced lessons more engaging and enjoyable compared to traditional teaching approaches. Technology allows students to have a more interactive and personalized learning experience, which increases their motivation to participate in class activities. Furthermore, students appreciate the flexibility that technology provides, enabling them to continue learning outside of the classroom at their own pace and on their own terms. This flexibility is particularly beneficial for fostering independent learning and helping students retain information more effectively.

However, despite these advantages, the full potential of technology in education is not always realized due to several barriers. A significant issue is the inadequate technological infrastructure at the school, which limits students' access to digital tools and resources. Additionally, distractions from social media and other digital platforms are major challenges that interfere with students' focus during lessons. Platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and other social media apps can divert students' attention away from their academic work, reducing the effectiveness of technology-based learning. To maximize the benefits of technology, it is crucial for the school to address these infrastructure issues, such as improving Wi-Fi access and providing sufficient devices for students, while also implementing strategies to help students manage distractions effectively. While the integration of technology at SMA Negeri 1 Telaga has shown great promise in enhancing the learning experience, there are still several challenges that need to be addressed. Ensuring that all teachers are proficient in using technology and improving the technological infrastructure of the school are key steps in fully harnessing the potential of technology in education. Moreover, finding ways to minimize distractions and encouraging responsible use of digital tools among students will further support the goal of providing an enriching, modern learning environment that prepares students for future success.

RECOMMENDATION

For students, it is recommended that they maximize the use of technology for independent learning outside the classroom. They can take advantage of the flexibility technology offers by using online platforms, educational apps, and tutorial videos to deepen the material taught in class. In addition, students need to manage digital distractions, such as social media, so that technology can fully support their learning. One way to do this is by setting specific study times and using apps to block irrelevant sites. Moreover, students are encouraged to be proactive in seeking help if they encounter difficulties, whether from teachers or classmates, to better understand the material and increase their engagement in learning.

For teachers, it is important to regularly attend training and workshops on integrating technology into learning. Through these trainings, teachers can become more skilled in utilizing various technological tools and educational apps to enhance student engagement in learning. Additionally, teachers are expected to create interactive and engaging lessons by incorporating elements such as quizzes, online discussions, and multimedia presentations, which can help cater to the diverse learning styles of students. Teachers should also set clear guidelines regarding the use of technology in the classroom to minimize distractions and ensure that technology is used effectively. Schools should provide support for teachers who struggle with technology by offering mentoring or collaboration opportunities between experienced teachers and those less familiar with technology.

For schools and stakeholders, it is crucial to provide adequate technological facilities, such as Wi-Fi that is accessible to all students throughout the school. A stable internet connection is essential to support technology-based learning, both in the classroom and for independent study. Schools should also provide equipment such as LCD projectors and speakers in every classroom to ensure more effective technology integration in lessons. Additionally, improving technological infrastructure,

including providing computers or tablets for every student, will create a more inclusive and adaptive learning environment that keeps up with the times.

For researchers, it is recommended to conduct further studies on the effectiveness of specific technological tools in language learning, such as PowerPoint, Canva, or other educational apps, to observe their impact on students' language skills. Researchers should also investigate the long-term impact of technology use in education, particularly in terms of student motivation and academic achievement. Identifying ways to address barriers caused by inadequate technological infrastructure in schools, such as limited access to devices and unstable internet connections, is also important. Research on teachers' digital literacy is also necessary to understand how teachers' digital skills affect the success of technology integration in classroom teaching.

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